

Rac-1ad

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-117-s-rac-20%AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0
Vial:	34	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 117 s rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/11/2021 9:34:35 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/12/2021 5:12:58 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.274	7466763	50.02	817354
2	7.975	7461290	49.98	611754

Asy-1ad

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-117-2-s-20%AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	10112
Vial:	33	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 117 3 s
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/11/2021 9:06:29 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/12/2021 5:11:28 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.224	1623317	8.79	176177
2	7.899	16847352	91.21	1357061